

SegRap: Segmentation of Gross Tumor Volume and Lymph Node Clinical Target Volume for Radiotherapy Planning of Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma Challenge 2025: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

SegRap: Segmentation of Gross Tumor Volume and Lymph Node Clinical Target Volume for Radiotherapy Planning of Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma Challenge 2025

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

SegRap2025

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Radiotherapy is one of the most important cancer treatments, which utilizes external beam radiation to kill cancer cells. Effective treatment planning is crucial for radiotherapy, which sets up the radiation dose distribution for tumor volumes. The goal of treatment planning is to maximize the likelihood of a cure while minimizing radiation-related toxicity. In radiotherapy planning, Gross Tumor Volume (GTV) and Clinical Target Volume (CTV) are two key volumes of interest. GTV is the position and extent of the primary tumor imaged by Computed Tomography (CT) scans, i.e., what is visible. CTV, which encompasses the GTV, describes the extent of microscopic, unimageable tumor spread. Accurately delineating the boundaries of GTV and CTV for Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma (NPC) from CT scans is a critical step in treatment planning. However, manual delineation slice-by-slice in CT scans is time-consuming and labor-intensive for radiation oncologists. Automating this process with precise delineation of GTV and CTV would significantly reduce treatment planning time, thereby improving the efficiency of radiotherapy.

We propose the “Segmentation of Gross Tumor Volume and Lymph Node Clinical Target Volume for Radiotherapy Planning of Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma Challenge 2025 (SegRap2025)”, to be held in conjunction with MICCAI 2025. This challenge will provide two datasets of CT scans from NPC patients for GTV and Lymph Node (LN) CTV segmentation. The GTV segmentation dataset consists of CT scans from 260 patients collected across two cohorts. Each patient has paired non-contrast CT (ncCT) and contrast-enhanced CT (ceCT) scans, with pixel-level annotations for Gross Tumor Volume of nasopharynx (GTVnx) and Gross Tumor Volume of lymph node (GTVnd). The LN CTV segmentation dataset includes CT scans from 402 patients across six cohorts, with 210 patients

having paired ncCT and ceCT scans, and 192 patients with either one ncCT or ceCT scan. All scans are annotated with pixel-level segmentations for LN CTV.

This challenge offers comprehensive datasets for automatic delineation of GTV and LN CTV, which provides valuable data to the research community. It is an extension of SegRap2023, which was held at MICCAI2023 for Organ-at-Risk (OAR) and GTV segmentation (387 teams registered, with 10 and 11 teams submitting their final models for OAR and GTV evaluation, respectively. The challenge talks and ceremony attracted a large group of audience to learn about the top-ranking methods). While most teams performed well for OAR segmentation, GTV segmentation remains a challenging problem. Hence, SegRap2025 will provide an extensive and comprehensive dataset with 260 patients and two GTVs from two cohorts. CT scans from one internal cohort will be used for training and validation, while scans from both the internal cohort and an external cohort will be used for testing, evaluating the generalizability of the model. Additionally, SegRap2025 will be the first challenge to focus on LN CTV segmentation with an extensive dataset of 402 patients from six cohorts. Multi- and single-modal CT scans from five cohorts will be used for training, with scans from another external cohort used for validation and testing. The challenge will address the issue of missing modalities in LN CTV delineation. Moreover, SegRap2025 will provide an unlabeled dataset of CT scans from 500 patients to aid in model training. Based on the extensive and comprehensive datasets, two sub-tasks will be held in SegRap2025:

Task01: Gross Tumor Volume (GTV) segmentation

Task02: Lymph Node Clinical Target Volume (LN CTV) segmentation

SegRap2025 is expected to continually attract much attention from the research community and advance the research on GTV and LN CTV segmentation significantly.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Gross Tumor Volume, Lymph Node Clinical Target Volume, Segmentation, Radiotherapy

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

N/A

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The SegRap2025 challenge comprises two primary tasks: Gross Tumor Volume (GTV) segmentation and Lymph Node (LN) Clinical Target Volume (CTV) segmentation. The GTV segmentation focuses on accurately delineating the primary treatment area of the gross tumor, and the LN CTV segmentation aims to accurately outline lymphatic drainage regions. These tasks enable a wide range of applications, including precise tumor localization and delineation, precise dose distribution calculation, and the development of personalized treatment planning by identifying specific tumors and lymph nodes. By advancing GTV and LN CTV segmentation methodologies, the challenge supports clinical manual delineation, enhances research on radiation dose calculation, and improves

efficiency of radiotherapy treatment planning.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

Based on the participation number (387) of SegRap2023, we anticipate attracting between 400 and 500 participants for SegRap2025.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes, after completing the challenge, we will prepare a summary report paper and submit it to a top journal.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

N/A

TASK 1: Gross Tumor Volume (GTV) segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Radiotherapy is one of the most important cancer treatments, which utilizes external beam radiation to kill cancer cells. Effective treatment planning is crucial for radiotherapy, which sets up the radiation dose distribution for tumor volumes. The goal of treatment planning is to maximize the likelihood of a cure while minimizing radiation-related toxicity. Gross Tumor Volume (GTV) is the position and extent of the primary tumor imaged by Computed Tomography (CT) scans, i.e., what is visible. Proper delineation of the GTVs enhances local control rates of the treatment and reduces the risk of recurrence. However, accurate delineation of GTVs is a significant challenge for junior radiation oncologists. Besides, manual delineation slice-by-slice in CT scans is time-consuming and labor-intensive for radiation oncologists. Accurately delineating Gross Tumor Volume of nasopharynx (GTVnx) and Gross Tumor Volume of lymph node (GTVnd) for nasopharyngeal carcinoma from CT scans would significantly reduce treatment planning time, thereby improving the efficiency of radiotherapy.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Gross Tumor Volume, Segmentation, Radiotherapy

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Jia Fu (University of Electronic Science and Technology of China)

Xiangde Luo (Sichuan Cancer Hospital & Institute, Sichuan Cancer Center)

He Li (University of Electronic Science and Technology of China)

Huamin Wang (University of Electronic Science and Technology of China)

Litingyu Wang (University of Electronic Science and Technology of China)

Shichuan Zhang (Sichuan Cancer Hospital & Institute, Sichuan Cancer Center)

Wenjun Liao (Sichuan Cancer Hospital & Institute, Sichuan Cancer Center)

Guotai Wang (University of Electronic Science and Technology of China)

Shaoting Zhang (University of Electronic Science and Technology of China, Shanghai Artificial Intelligence Laboratory)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jia Fu (jia.fu@std.uestc.edu.cn)

Guotai Wang (guotai.wang@uestc.edu.cn), the challenge leader.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

N/A

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

We will release a website to announce the challenge, release the dataset, and publish the results. All algorithms will be evaluated on the same GPU desktop workstation. The workstation is a Ubuntu 20.04 desktop with one CPU (Inter (R) Core (TM) i9-10940X, 3.30 GHz×14 cores), one GPU (NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090, 24G), 64 G of memory.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

None at this moment.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

To incentivize participation and acknowledgment, the SegRap2025 challenge will offer a structured award policy comprising monetary prizes, recognition, and opportunities for further collaboration. The top five teams of each task will be invited to present talks and winning certificates will be provided. Monetary prizes will be awarded to the top three teams for each task demonstrating the highest performance based on the final rank score of their solutions in the challenge tasks. The detailed monetary prizes are as follows:

First place: \$ 1,000

Second place: \$ 600

Third place: \$ 400

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Scores and rankings of all participating teams will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Only teams that submit their final results for evaluation in the SegRap2025 challenge are qualified as authors of the challenge paper. After completing the challenge, all participating teams may publish their own results separately. All publications must cite the SegRap2025 Challenge and its official challenge paper (if available), ensuring proper acknowledgment of the dataset and participation.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container and command to execute the container should be sent to the organizers for local evaluation. All testing images will not be publicly available. Submission instructions can be found on Github:
https://github.com/HiLab-git/SegRap2023/tree/main/Docker_tutorial.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We allow five times submissions on the validation set and only one successful submission on the testing set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)

- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

a) Registration opens: May 1st (12:00AM GMT), 2025;

Participants can register for the challenge with the registration period starting from the possible date of May 1st, 2025, until Aug. 10th, 2025.

b) Release of training data: May 10th (12:00AM GMT), 2025;

Participants can use the training dataset to train their own models.

c) Release of validation data: June 1st (12:00AM GMT), 2025;

Participants can submit their segmentation results of the validation dataset to the organization team once per week. A maximum of five submissions are allowed during the validation stage to ensure fair evaluation and prevent overfitting.

d) Docker and short paper submission of the testing set opening: Aug. 10th (12:00AM GMT), 2025;

Participants must prepare and submit their Docker containers along with a short paper outlining their method.

e) Submission deadline for results: Aug. 31st (12:00AM GMT), 2025;

Participants should complete the submission before the deadline.

f) Announcement of final results: Sept. 25th, 2025.

We will announce the final rankings and awards.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval on data has been obtained, and we have uploaded it as supplementary material at:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/19XdgP2EdUq6bcQ6slzmXICrIgo8DG1O4/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=104340132441831399252&rtpof=true&sd=true>.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made public before the system is open for submission. The evaluation metric can be found in <https://loli.github.io/medpy> and https://medicaldecathlon.com/files/Surface_distance_based_measures.ipynb.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

All participating teams must release their code and pre-trained model for final ranking.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizers will have access to the test case labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Assistance, Treatment planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection

- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The samples in our dataset are sourced from cancer patients.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The samples in our dataset are sourced from cancer patients.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

CT (non-contrast and contrast-enhanced).

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Pixel-level GTV segmentation annotations.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Patients with nasopharyngeal cancer before/after treatment.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Head and neck CT scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

GTVnx and GTVnd in head and neck CT scans.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Precision, Accuracy

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

CT images are collected by Siemens CT scanners with the following scanning conditions: bulb voltage, 120 kV; current, 300 mA; scan thickness, 3.0 mm; resolution, body cropped from full resolution of 1024×1024 ; injected contrast agent, iohexol (volume, 60–80 mL; rate, 2 mL/s; without delay).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Non-contrast and contrast-enhanced CT scans.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Sichuan Cancer Hospital and Institute, Sichuan Cancer Center, Chengdu, China.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All images were collected, checked, and refined by W. Liao (MD, with ten years of experience in oncology radiation therapy) and S. Zhang (MD, with more than twenty years of experience in oncology radiation therapy) and their team. The annotation tools are MIMSoftware (original delineation for radiation therapy plans) and ITK-SNAP (annotation check).

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Two GTVs from each patient's head and neck CT scan, including Gross Tumor Volume of nasopharynx (GTVnx) and Gross Tumor Volume of lymph node (GTVnd).

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training: 120 labeled cases and 500 unlabeled cases from Cohort 1

Validation: 20 cases from Cohort 1

Testing: 60 cases from Cohort 1 and 60 cases from Cohort 2

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

There are a total of 200 patients from Cohort 1, where 60%, 10%, and 30% of them are used for training, validation, and testing. In addition, to evaluate the generalizability of models, CT scans from 60 patients from Cohort 2 are used for testing.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Data from Cohort 1 is randomly split into the training, validation and testing set. They are assumed to have the same distribution (gender and age).

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

SegRap2025 provides a new unlabeled dataset with CT scans from 500 NPC patients for model training, and a new external dataset with CT scans from 60 NPC patients for model testing. The proportion of new data is about 73.68%.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Pixel-level annotations of the GTVs are from real radiation therapy plans following a clinical practice (using MIMSoftware). Then two annotators checked these annotations using ITK-SNAP together.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

All annotations are from real radiation therapy plans following a clinical practice (produced by S. Zhang's and W. Liao's group using MIMSoftware). Two annotators checked these annotations using ITK-SNAP together.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Experienced oncologists (W. Liao with ten years of experience in oncology radiation therapy and S. Zhang with more than twenty years of experience in oncology radiation therapy) who have performed hundreds of radiation therapy plans.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Patient-identity information is removed from data to protect the patient's privacy.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

In the annotation and refinement stage, MD. W. Liao and Prof. S. Zhang were invited to identify and refine all original delineations together to obey the standard RTOG atlas and produce consensus annotations. Then we selected 260 patients to constitute the dataset, where these images have annotations for GTV and the mean Hausdorff distance between the original delineations and the final refinements is smaller than 3mm (all mean dice scores are between 0.94-1.0).

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

1. Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC);
2. Normalized Surface Dice (NSD).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The two metrics are widely used to measure segmentation accuracy.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Firstly, for each GTV, we calculate the average DSC and NSD across all patients, respectively. Secondly, each participant will be ranked based on the class-level DSC and NSD; each participant will have 2*2 rankings. Finally, average all these rankings and then normalize them by the number of teams. At the same time, we will take the statistical ranking. (Allow equal teams if there is no significant difference)

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If the submissions have some missing results on test cases, the corresponding class's DSC and NSD will be set to 0 and 0.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different GTVs. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in the MICCAI BraTS Challenge 2017-2020 and the SegRap 2023 Challenge. It is also transparent and fair to the participants.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

(a) Overall performance: For each algorithm, we will calculate the average DSC and NSD to evaluate segmentation performance, with higher values indicating better rankings. In the final ranking calculation, we will sum and average the rankings of the two metrics, with lower values indicating better performance. The algorithm's overall performance can be measured by the average rankings across all cases (The standard ranking scheme has previously been employed in other challenges with satisfactory results, such as the BraTS2019 and the SegRap2023 challenges.).

(b) Algorithm stability: The standard deviation of the average ranking for each algorithm can measure its stability. If several algorithms have the same average ranking, we will consider using the standard deviation to reflect the stability of the algorithms.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

To analyze the stability of the ranking scheme, we will employ the bootstrapping method detailed in Wiesenfarth et al. (2021).

Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. Scientific Reports 11, 2369 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-82017-6>

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

To analyze the stability of the ranking scheme, we will employ the bootstrapping method detailed in Wiesenfarth et al. (2021).

Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. Scientific Reports 11, 2369 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-82017-6>

TASK 2: Lymph Node (LN) Clinical Target Volume (CTV) segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Radiotherapy is one of the most important cancer treatments, which utilizes external beam radiation to kill cancer cells. Effective treatment planning is crucial for radiotherapy, which sets up the radiation dose distribution for tumor volumes. The goal of treatment planning is to maximize the likelihood of a cure while minimizing radiation-related toxicity. Clinical Target Volume (CTV), which encompasses the GTV, describes the extent of microscopic, unimageable tumor spread. Accurately delineating the boundaries of Lymph Node (LN) Clinical Target Volume (CTV) for Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma (NPC) from CT scans is a critical step in treatment planning. However, manual delineation slice-by-slice in CT scans is time-consuming and labor-intensive for radiation oncologists. Automatically delineating LN CTVs for nasopharyngeal carcinoma from CT scans would substantially reduce treatment planning time and thereby improve the efficiency of radiotherapy.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Lymph Node Clinical Target Volume, Segmentation, Radiotherapy

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Jia Fu (University of Electronic Science and Technology of China)

Xiangde Luo (Sichuan Cancer Hospital & Institute, Sichuan Cancer Center)

He Li (University of Electronic Science and Technology of China)

Huamin Wang (University of Electronic Science and Technology of China)

Litingyu Wang (University of Electronic Science and Technology of China)

Shichuan Zhang (Sichuan Cancer Hospital & Institute, Sichuan Cancer Center)

Wenjun Liao (Sichuan Cancer Hospital & Institute, Sichuan Cancer Center)

Guotai Wang (University of Electronic Science and Technology of China)

Shaoting Zhang (University of Electronic Science and Technology of China, Shanghai Artificial Intelligence Laboratory)

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Jia Fu (jia.fu@std.uestc.edu.cn)

Guotai Wang (guotai.wang@uestc.edu.cn), the challenge leader.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
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Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

N/A

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

We will release a website to announce the challenge, release the dataset, and publish the results. All algorithms will be evaluated on the same GPU desktop workstation. The workstation is a Ubuntu 20.04 desktop with one CPU (Inter (R) Core (TM) i9-10940X, 3.30 GHz×14 cores), one GPU (NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090, 24G), 64 G of memory.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

None at this moment.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

No additional data allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

To incentivize participation and acknowledgment, the SegRap2025 challenge will offer a structured award policy comprising monetary prizes, recognition, and opportunities for further collaboration. The top five teams of each task will be invited to present talks and winning certificates will be provided. Monetary prizes will be awarded to the top three teams for each task demonstrating the highest performance based on the final rank score of their solutions in the challenge tasks. The detailed monetary prizes are as follows:

First place: \$ 1,000

Second place: \$ 600

Third place: \$ 400

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Scores and rankings of all participating teams will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Only teams that submit their final results for evaluation in the SegRap2025 challenge are qualified as authors of the challenge paper. After completing the challenge, all participating teams may publish their own results separately. All publications must cite the SegRap2025 Challenge and its official challenge paper (if available), ensuring proper acknowledgment of the dataset and participation.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container and command to execute the container should be sent to the organizers for local evaluation. All testing images will not be publicly available. Submission instructions can be found on Github:

https://github.com/HiLab-git/SegRap2023/tree/main/Docker_tutorial.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We allow five times submissions on the validation set and only one successful submission on the testing set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)

- associated workshop days (if any)

- the release date(s) of the results

a) Registration opens: May 1st (12:00AM GMT), 2025;

Participants can register for the challenge with the registration period starting from the possible date of May 1st, 2025, until Aug. 10th, 2025.

b) Release of training data: May 10th (12:00AM GMT), 2025;

Participants can use the training dataset to train their own models.

c) Release of validation data: June 1st (12:00AM GMT), 2025;

Participants can submit their segmentation results of the validation dataset to the organization team once per week. A maximum of five submissions are allowed during the validation stage to ensure fair evaluation and prevent overfitting.

d) Docker and short paper submission of the testing set opening: Aug. 10th (12:00AM GMT), 2025;

Participants must prepare and submit their Docker containers along with a short paper outlining their method.

e) Submission deadline for results: Aug. 31st (12:00AM GMT), 2025;

Participants should complete the submission before the deadline.

f) Announcement of final results: Sept. 25th, 2025.

We will announce the final rankings and awards.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval on data has been obtained, and we have uploaded it as supplementary material at:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/19XdgP2EdUq6bcQ6slzmXICrIgo8DG1O4/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=104340132441831399252&rtpof=true&sd=true>

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)

- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)

- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)

- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made public before the system is open for submission. The evaluation metric can be found in <https://loli.github.io/medpy> and https://medicaldecathlon.com/files/Surface_distance_based_measures.ipynb.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

All participating teams must release their code and pre-trained model for final ranking.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizers will have access to the test case labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Assistance, Treatment planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection

- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The samples in our dataset are sourced from cancer patients.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The samples in our dataset are sourced from cancer patients.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

CT (non-contrast and contrast-enhanced).

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Pixel-level LN CTV segmentation annotations.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Patients with nasopharyngeal cancer before/after treatment.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Head and neck CT scans.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Six basic LN CTVs in head and neck CT scans**Assessment aim(s)**

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Precision, Accuracy

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

CT images from Sichuan Cancer Hospital are collected by a Brilliance CT Big Bore system from Philips Healthcare (Philips Healthcare, Best, the Netherlands), with the following scanning conditions: bulb voltage at 120 kV, current ranging from 275 to 375 mA, slice thickness of 3.0 mm, and full resolution of 512×512 . An injected contrast agent, iohexol, was used during the ceCT examination. Similarly, CT images from Sichuan Provincial People's Hospital, The First Affiliated Hospital of University of Science and Technology of China and Southern Medical University were acquired using a Somatom Definition AS 40 system from Siemens Healthcare (Siemens Healthcare, Forchheim, Germany), with the following conditions: bulb voltage ranging from 120 to 140 kV, current ranging from 280 to 380 mA, slice thickness of 3.0 mm, and full resolution of 512×512 . CT images from Daguang Hospital of Chengdu Jinjiang were acquired using a Somatom Definition AS 40 system from Siemens Healthcare (Siemens Healthcare, Forchheim, Germany), with the following conditions: bulb voltage 120 kV, current ranging from 200 to 250 mA, slice thickness of 2.5 mm, and full resolution of 512×512 .

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Non-contrast and contrast-enhanced CT scans.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

1. Sichuan Cancer Hospital and Institute, Sichuan Cancer Center, Chengdu, China.
2. Cancer Center, Sichuan Provincial People's Hospital, University of Electronic Science and Technology of China,

Chengdu, China.

3. Department of Radiation Oncology, The First Affiliated Hospital of University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei, China.

4. Department of Radiation Oncology, Nanfang Hospital, Southern Medical University, Guangzhou, China.

5. Department of Radiation Oncology, Dagan Hospital of Chengdu Jinjiang, Chengdu, China.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All images were collected, checked, and refined by the clinical expert board (comprising two experts).

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Six LN CTVs from each patient's head and neck CT scan, including levels L_Ib, L_II+III+Va, L_IV+Vb+Vc, R_Ib, R_II+III+Va, R_IV+Vb+Vc.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training: 262 labeled cases from Cohort 1-5 and 500 unlabeled cases from Cohort 1

Validation: 40 cases from Cohort 6

Testing: 100 cases from Cohort 6

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

To evaluate the capability of models to address data distribution and missing modality problems, there are 262 patients from Cohort 1 to 5 (about 65%) are used for training. A total of 40 (about 10%) and 100 (about 25%) patients from Cohort 6 are used for validation and testing, respectively.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Data from Cohort 6 is randomly split into the validation and testing set. They are assumed to have the same distribution (gender and age).

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

SegRap2025 provides a new unlabeled dataset with CT scans from 500 NPC patients for model training, and a new external dataset with CT scans from 140 NPC patients for model validation and testing. The proportion of new

data is about 70.95%.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Pixel-level annotations of the LN CTVs for each cohort are manually delineated by the clinical expert board, which comprises two experts.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

All annotations are manually delineated by the clinical expert board. Two annotators checked these annotations using ITK-SNAP together.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Experts in the clinical expert board have more than ten years of experience in oncology radiation therapy.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Patient-identity information is removed from data to protect the patient's privacy.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

In the annotation and refinement stage, experts were invited to identify and refine all original delineations together to obey the standard RTOG atlas and produce consensus annotations. Then we selected 402 patients to constitute the dataset, where these images have annotations for LN CTV and the mean Hausdorff distance between the original delineations and the final refinements is smaller than 3mm (all mean dice scores are between 0.94-1.0).

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

1. Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC);
2. Normalized Surface Dice (NSD).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The two metrics are widely used to measure segmentation accuracy.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Firstly, for each LN CTV, we calculate the average DSC and NSD across all patients, respectively. Secondly, each participant will be ranked based on the class-level DSC and NSD; each participant will have 6*2 rankings. Finally, average all these rankings and then normalize them by the number of teams. At the same time, we will take the statistical ranking. (Allow equal teams if there is no significant difference)

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If the submissions have some missing results on test cases, the corresponding class's DSC and NSD will be set to 0 and 0.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different LN CTVs. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in the MICCAI BraTS Challenge 2017-2020 and the SegRap 2023 Challenge. It is also transparent and fair to the participants.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

(a) Overall performance: For each algorithm, we will calculate the average DSC and NSD to evaluate segmentation performance, with higher values indicating better rankings. In the final ranking calculation, we will sum and average the rankings of the two metrics, with lower values indicating better performance. The algorithm's overall performance can be measured by the average rankings across all cases (The standard ranking scheme has

previously been employed in other challenges with satisfactory results, such as the BraTS2019 and the SegRap2023 challenges.).

(b) Algorithm stability: The standard deviation of the average ranking for each algorithm can measure its stability. If several algorithms have the same average ranking, we will consider using the standard deviation to reflect the stability of the algorithms.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

To analyze the stability of the ranking scheme, we will employ the bootstrapping method detailed in Wiesenfarth et al. (2021).

Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. *Scientific Reports* 11, 2369 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-82017-6>

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

To analyze the stability of the ranking scheme, we will employ the bootstrapping method detailed in Wiesenfarth et al. (2021).

Wiesenfarth, M., Reinke, A., Landman, B.A. et al. Methods and open-source toolkit for analyzing and visualizing challenge results. *Scientific Reports* 11, 2369 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-82017-6>

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

Challenge design can refer to SegRap2023: <https://segrap2023.grand-challenge.org/>, code and data can refer to <https://github.com/HiLab-git/SegRap2023> and <https://github.com/Luoxd1996/LNCTVSeg>.

Luo, X., Fu, J., et al. Segrap2023: A benchmark of organs-at-risk and gross tumor volume segmentation for radiotherapy planning of nasopharyngeal carcinoma [J]. *Medical Image Analysis* 2025, 101: 103447. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2024.103447>

Luo, X., Liao, W., Zhao, Y. et al. A multicenter dataset for lymph node clinical target volume delineation of nasopharyngeal carcinoma. *Scientific Data* 11, 1085 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03890-0>

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A.